

NATIONAL-CULTURAL FEATURES OF PARAPHRASES (IN THE EXAMPLE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)

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Abstract:

This article provides a comparative analysis of the linguocultural features of periphrases in English and Uzbek. Periphrases are evaluated as national-cultural codes reflecting the history, beliefs, and lifestyle of the people. Examples reveal the specific features of secondary naming in different languages.

Key words:

periphrasis, linguoculturology, national-cultural feature, cultural code, secondary naming, linguistic worldview.

Introduction

In modern linguistics, the study of linguistic phenomena not only from a structural-semantic perspective but also from a linguoculturological approach is becoming increasingly relevant. Although paraphrases, which are a means of secondary naming of objects and reality, have long been an object of methodological research, today they are being reevaluated as an important tool that carries the linguocultural codes of society. Paraphrases directly reflect the national mentality, customs, and values of a particular people [Ashurova, 2016:45]. Therefore, the comparative study of paraphrases in different systematic languages, in particular, in the case of English and Uzbek, is of great practical importance in revealing the commonalities and specificities in the linguistic perception of the world of two nations.

Paraphrases and national mentality

The linguoculturological approach is based on the inextricable link between language and culture. As linguist V. Maslova notes, language is a treasure trove of culture, the main means of transmitting cultural values from generation to generation [Maslova, 2001:56]. Paraphrases are considered units that actively preserve these cultural codes and reflect them in speech. As a result of the mutual integration of cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology, language units, in particular paraphrases, began to be interpreted as a means of forming a certain linguistic landscape in the human mind [Safarov, 2006:32]. V.N. Telia recognizes that such figurative units of language and secondary naming devices serve as a kind of mirror of the cultural and national worldview of the people [Telia, 1996:89].

Paraphrases in English and Uzbek have their own linguocultural characteristics, which are closely related to the history, geographical location and lifestyle of the people. For example, in Great Britain, which has a rich ancient history and the status of an island state, paraphrases related to the sea, shipping, and monarchy are very common. Great Britain is often represented by paraphrases of a national-cultural nature, such as "*the Mistress of the Seas*" or "*Foggy Albion*." These secondary names clearly express the maritime traditions and specific climatic conditions inherent in the nature of the English people.

Cultural codes and secondary naming

In the Uzbek language, paraphrases relating to cultural and historical centers, agricultural traditions, and the Islamic religion are very actively used in our speech. For example, the city of Samarkand is described "*Yer yuzining sayqali*" or "*Moviy gumbazlar shahri*". Paraphrases such as "*Jannatmakon o'lka*" (land of paradise) to describe Uzbekistan, and "*oq oltin*" (white gold) to

describe cotton, which is considered the economic wealth of our republic, demonstrate how much hospitality, love for the motherland, and hard work are valued in our culture [Yuldoshev, 2018:72].

Cultural differences are also evident in the representation of social roles. The paraphrases "*ma'rifat ziyosini tarqatuvchilar*" for teachers or "*umid g'unchalari*" for children are used in Uzbek based on the cultural frames of filial piety and respect for teachers that are characteristic of the Uzbek people [Mahmudov, 2012:38]. These examples show that the linguistic and cultural connotation plays a decisive role in the semantic structure of the paraphrase, adding an additional national-emotional value to the objective meaning of the word.

Conclusion

Linguistic-cultural analysis of paraphrases in English and Uzbek shows that the phenomenon of secondary naming is not only a logical-semantic process in the language system but also a specific reflection of cognitive processes as well as national culture, history, and geographical environment. In the process of comparative analysis, paraphrases allow us to identify different cultural models of the linguistic assessment of the world of two nations. Each language imprints the beliefs and values of its speakers in paraphrases. Future research in this area will serve to create practical applications in the fields of translation studies, sociolinguistics, and lexicography.

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